

Biomass-derived electrospun carbon nanofiber networks for high-performance supercapacitors

Ph.D student: Jiayuan Wei
Supervisor: Prof. Kristiina Oksman

Luleå University of Technology
University of Oulu
University of Toronto

Facts about lignin

- Lignin is the second most abundant biopolymers.
- Can be found in wood, grass and algae.

Facts about lignin

- Annually, 60 million tons of lignin is produced in pulping industry;
- Most of the lignin produced is burnt for thermal energy.

Facts about lignin

- Lignin has abundant aromatic structures;
- It represents approx. 30 % of all the non-fossil organic carbon on Earth;

Our goal

To make lignin-based carbon materials used as electrodes in supercapacitors

Preparation of lignin-based nanofibers

Electrospinning of lignin-based solution

Solid content: 20 wt%
Lignin: PVA ratio = 75:25

SEM image of the as-spun fibers

Stabilization

Photograph of the stabilized sample

SEM image of the stabilized fibers

Carbonization
800 - 1400°C

Photograph of the carbonized sample

SEM image of fibers carbonized
at 1400 °C

Showcase of the flexibility

Scale bar: 15 mm

Effects of temperature

Carbonization temperature:

800 °C

1000 °C

1200 °C

1400 °C

effects on

Microstructure

Carbon content

Surface area

Electrochemical properties

Carbon content and surface area

	Carbon (at%)	BET surface area (m ³ /g)
C800	87.6	797
C1000	94.8	946
C1200	97.7	1672
C1400	99.0	1419

Performance in supercapacitors

Charge/discharge with a constant voltage increment rate (20 mV/s)

Charge/discharge with a constant current (1 A/g)

GCD curves of all carbonized samples

Performance in supercapacitors

Specific capacitance calculated from CV curves and the water contact angle of all samples

All solid-state supercapacitors

Conclusions

- Lignin-based carbon nanofiber networks were successfully made via electrospinning and thermal carbonization;
- Effects of carbonization temperature on the microstructure, carbon content, surface area and electrochemical performance were studied;
- The carbonized networks have outstanding performance as electrodes in supercapacitors using both aqueous and solid-state electrolyte.

Acknowledgements

- Swedish Research Council, Bio4Energy for financial support
- Dr. Liang Yu and Mojtaba Nobandegani at Division of Chemical Technology at Luleå University of Technology for the surface area measurement;
- Linn Berglund at Division of Material Science at Luleå University of Technology for the contact angle measurements.

LULEÅ
UNIVERSITY
OF TECHNOLOGY

